

TIME-TEMPERATURE DEPENDENT COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOR OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP

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SUMMARY: The objective of this work is to propose a prediction scheme of the master curve of the compressive strength for CFRP strand and to assess its validity through the comparison with experimental results. Our scheme is an extension of Rosen's analysis [8,9] for compressive failure of unidirectional fibrous composites with elastic matrix to CFRP with viscoelastic matrix by substituting the value of relaxation modulus of polymer matrix at the time of failure for elastic modulus in Rosen's formula. The compression test for CFRP strand was carried out at various temperatures and loading rates and the master curve of the compressive strength together with the shift factor was obtained. The master curve for CFRP strength predicted by the proposed method captured the test results adequately cover the entire range tested.

KEYWORDS: Unidirectional CFRP, Compressive Strength, Time-Temperature Dependence, Prediction of Compressive Strength

1. INTRODUCTION

The mechanical behavior of polymer resin exhibits time and temperature dependence, called viscoelastic behavior, not only above the glass-transition temperature T_g but also below T_g . Thus, it can be presumed that the fracture behavior of CFRP using polymer resin as matrix also depends on time and temperature even below T_g which is within the normal operating-temperature range. These examples are shown by Aboudi et al. [1], Sullivan [2], Gates [3], and Miyano et al. [4].

In our previous papers [5,6], tensile strength of resin impregnated carbon fiber strand (CFRP strand) were measured under various constant strain-rates (CSR) and temperatures. The tensile strength thus obtained is plotted against failure time in logarithmic scale for each test temperature. By choosing a reference temperature and shifting these curves horizontally toward the curve for the reference temperature, we were able to construct a master curve of tensile strength indicating the validity of the time-temperature superposition principle, the shift factor for the tensile strength is found to be almost coincident with that for storage modulus of the matrix resin. Furthermore, we proposed a prediction scheme of the master curve of the tensile strength for CFRP strand and confirmed its validity through the comparison with experimental results [7].

The objective of this work is to propose a prediction scheme of the master curve of the compressive strength for CFRP strand and to assess its validity through the comparison with experimental results. Our scheme is an extension of Rosen's analysis [8,9] for compressive failure of unidirectional fibrous composites with elastic matrix to CFRP with viscoelastic matrix by substituting the value of relaxation modulus of polymer matrix at the time of failure for elastic modulus in Rosen's formula. The compression test for CFRP strand was carried out at various temperatures and loading rates. Applying the same construction scheme for master curve as for tensile strength, the master curve for compressive strength together with the shift factor was obtained. The master curve for CFRP strength predicted by the proposed method captured the test results adequately cover the entire range tested.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Shear relaxation modulus for resin in CFRP

We present here a procedure to estimate the relaxation modulus for resin in unidirectional CFRP from double cantilever test for the CFRP beam of length L with elliptical cross section of width B and height H . The central deflection is held at a constant value ε and the time variation of reactive force $P(t_r, T)$ under temperature T is recorded where we use t_r to emphasize the time for relaxation. We define an apparent tensile relaxation modulus by

$$F(t_r, T) = \frac{L^3}{3\pi BH^3} \frac{P(t_r, T)}{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

Since the elastic modulus for the fibers is much larger than that for matrix, the elastic modulus for the composite represented by the rule of mixture [10] may be written as

$$E_c = V_f E_f, \quad G_c(t_r, T) = \frac{1}{1 - V_f} G_m(t_r, T) \quad (2)$$

where E , G , V represent Young's modulus, shear modulus, fiber volume fraction and subscripts c, f, m imply the quantities for composite, fiber and matrix, respectively. The deflection ε consists of two parts: one corresponding to bending deformation and another due to shear deformation:

$$\varepsilon(t_r, T) = \frac{P(t_r, T)L^3}{3\pi BH^3} \left[\frac{1}{V_f E_f} + \frac{3(1 - V_f)}{G_m(t_r, T)} \left(\frac{H}{L} \right)^2 \right] \quad (3)$$

We suppose here that E_f and the glassy value of shear modulus G_{mg} for the matrix resin have been determined or known by some means. Now, let $\Phi(t_r, T)$ be the dimensionless apparent tensile relaxation modulus normalized by its glassy value F_g . Then, $\Phi(t_r, T)$ is equal to the ratio of reactive force $P(t_r, T)$ to its glassy value P_g in view of (1) and is represented in terms of the ratio between shear moduli by use of (2) and (3):

$$\Phi(t_r, T) = \frac{F(t_r, T)}{F_g} = \frac{P(t_r, T)}{P_g} = \frac{1 + C}{G_{mg} / G_m(t_r, T) + C} \quad (4)$$

where

$$C = \frac{G_{mg}}{3V_f(1 - V_f)E_f} \left(\frac{L}{H} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

Solving (4) for $G_m(t_r, T) / G_{mg}$, we have

$$\frac{G_m(t_r, T)}{G_{mg}} = \frac{\Phi(t_r, T)}{1 + C[1 - \Phi(t_r, T)]} \quad (6)$$

2.2 Compressive strength of CFRP

According to the theory of the compressive strength for unidirectionally oriented composite described by Rosen [8,9], the strength should be given by one of the following equations:

$$\sigma_c = 2V_f \left(\frac{V_f E_m E_f}{3(1 - V_f)} \right)^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_c = \frac{G_m}{1 - V_f} \quad (8)$$

Equation (7) is for the case where the fibers buckle in anti-phase and produces the extension mode deformation in the matrix. Equation (8) describes the situation where the fibers buckle in phase and deform the matrix in shear. This is then called the shear mode deformation of the matrix.

To see the time and temperature dependence of the compressive strength $\sigma_s(t_s, T)$ of unidirectional CFRP clearly, we introduce the the compressive strength ratio $\sigma_s(t_s, T)$ to σ_{sg} , where σ_{sg} is the compressive strength at glassy state. The ratio $\sigma_s(t_s, T)/\sigma_{sg}$ is obtained through Rosen's strength formula.

$$\frac{\sigma_s(t_s, T)}{\sigma_{sg}} = \left(\frac{E_m(t_r, T)}{E_{mg}} \right)^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_s(t_s, T)}{\sigma_{sg}} = \frac{G_m(t_r, T)}{G_{mg}} \quad (10)$$

where $E_m(t_r, T)$ and $G_m(t_r, T)$ are the tensile and shear relaxation moduli which depend on time and temperature. E_{mg} and G_{mg} are the tensile and shear moduli at glassy state. We can estimate $\sigma_s(t_s, T)$ if we know σ_{sg} at glassy state, the tensile and shear moduli ratio $E_m(t_r, T)/E_{mg}$ and $G_m(t_r, T)/G_{mg}$.

3. EXPERIMENT

3.1 Specimen

Epoxy resin impregnated carbon fiber strand (CFRP strand) was employed as the compression test specimen along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP. CFRP strand consists of high strength carbon fibers TORAYCA® T300-3K (TORAY) and a general-purpose epoxy resin EPIKOTE® 828 (YUKA SHELL EPOXY). The composition of epoxy resin and cure condition for the CFRP strand is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Composition of epoxy resin and cure condition for CFRP strand

Resin composition		Weight ratio
Epoxy	:Epikote 828	100
Hardener	:Methyl himic anhidride	103.6
Cure accelerator	:2-Ethyl-4-methylimidazol	1
Cure Condition		
70°C × 12h+150°C × 4h+190°C × 2h+110°C × 167h		

3.2 Dynamic double cantilever test

The dynamic double cantilever tests were conducted at sixteen angular velocities ω (0.01rad/sec to 50rad/sec) and fourteen temperature levels listed in Fig.3. Schematic diagram of the dynamic test setup is shown in Fig.1. The span L is 36.7mm. The dynamic storage modulus $F'(\omega, T)$ is the dynamic counterpart of the apparent relaxation modulus $F(t_r, T)$ defined by (1) to which the dynamic storage modulus can be converted approximately using Christensen's formula [11].

Fig.1 Schematic diagram of the dynamic double cantilever test

3.3 Compression test of CFRP strand at various strain rates and temperatures

The compression tests for CFRP strand along the fiber direction were carried out under various loading-rates and temperatures using an Instron type testing machine with a temperature chamber as shown in Fig.2 which also includes the dimensions of the specimen and the grip end to which the ends of specimen are adhesively bonded. Loading rates (cross-head speeds) were 0.01, 0.1, 1, and 10mm/min. The compressive fracture of all CFRP strands tested occurred within the central 1.4mm region of the specimen. The compressive strength $\sigma_s(t_s, T)$ of CFRP strand can be obtained by equation (11),

$$\sigma_s(t_s, T) = P_{\max}(t_s, T) \frac{\rho}{t_e} \quad (11)$$

Fig.2 Configuration of specimen and method of compression test for CFRP strand where P_{\max} , ρ , t_e are the maximum load [N] of the CFRP strand, the fiber density and the tex of fiber strand [(g/m) $\times 10^6$], respectively. Therefore, the compressive strength of CFRP strand is calculated using the cross sectional area of carbon fiber bundle in the strand.

4. RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

4.1 Shear relaxation modulus for matrix resin in CFRP

The dynamic storage modulus $F'(\omega, T)$ measured in 3.2 was converted to the apparent tensile relaxation modulus $F(t_r, T)$ described in 2.1 using the approximate formula [11]:

$$F'(\omega, T) \Big|_{\omega=2/(\pi t_r)} \approx F(t_r, T) \quad (12)$$

where t_r is the time for relaxation. In the left side of Fig.3, the dimensionless relaxation modulus $\Phi(t_r, T) = F(t_r, T)/F_g$ defined by (4) is presented against logarithmic time scale for various temperatures. Shifting the curves other than the one for the reference temperature $T_0=50^\circ\text{C}$ horizontally so that they overlap on each other, we obtain a single smooth master curve against the reduced time t_r' as shown in

the right hand side of this figure. A smooth curve thus obtained indicates the validity of the time-temperature superposition principle for the relaxation modulus.

Here, we define the shift factor at a reference temperature T_0 for a response x by

$$a_{T_0;x}(T) = \frac{t_x}{t_x'} \quad (13)$$

where t_x, t_x' are the relevant physical time and the associated time, respectively. The shift factors for the relaxation modulus F obtained in the construction process of master curve are shown in Fig.4 where we set $x=r$ indicating the relaxation.

The shift factors for the relaxation modulus are in good agreement with two Arrhenius equations with $\Delta H_1=143\text{kJ/mol}$ and $\Delta H_2=673\text{kJ/mol}$:

$$\log a_{T_0;x}(T) = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \quad (14)$$

where G is gas constant, $8.314 \times 10^{-3} [\text{kJ}/(\text{mol} \cdot \text{K})]$.

The master curve for dimensionless shear relaxation modulus $G_m(t_r, T)/G_{mg}$ for the matrix resin in CFRP was constructed from the master curve for the dimensionless apparent tensile relaxation modulus $\Phi(t_r', T_0) = F(t_r', T_0)/F_g$ in Fig.3 by use of (6) and is exhibited in Fig.5.

Fig.3 Apparent relaxation modulus for CFRP strand and its master curve

Fig.4 Shift factors of storage modulus for CFRP strand

Fig.5 Dimensionless shear relaxation modulus for matrix resin

4.2 Master curve of compressive strength

The compressive strength $\sigma_s(t_s, T)$ for CFRP strand versus time to failure t_s at various temperatures T are shown in the left side of Fig.6. The time-temperature shift factor for apparent relaxation modulus of CFRP strand is used to shift the data on the left side to the right side against the reduced time at the reference temperature 50°C where the failure data are inherently scattered. Using $E_m(t_r', T_0)/E_{mg}$ shown in Fig.5, the compressive strength ratio $\sigma_s(t_s', T_0)/\sigma_{sg}$ in the extension mode is predicted based on (9) as shown by the solid curve, while that in the shear mode is predicted on the basis of (10) as shown by the dotted curve. The predicted curve for the extension mode captures the test data adequately confirming the validity of time-temperature superposition principle for compressive strength to some extent. On the other hand, that for the shear mode overestimates the test data at low temperatures and underestimates at high temperatures.

Fig.6 Master curve of compressive strength for CFRP strand

5. CONCLUSION

We converted Rosen's strength formula for fiber reinforced composite with elastic matrix to the formula for CFRP strength by certain adjustments pertinent for polymer matrix.

The data for the compressive CFRP strength under various temperatures and loading rates were found to obey the time-temperature superposition principle with the shift factor which is same with that for the storage modulus of CFRP strand. The master curve predicted based on the extension mode

captures the test data adequately over the entire range tested. It was shown experimentally and theoretically that the time and temperature dependence of the compressive CFRP strength is controlled by the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin.

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